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Comparative Study and Analysis of the Capital City of Chandigarh- Two Master Plans by Albert Mayer, Mathew Nowicki & Le- Corbusier

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ABSTRACT

Morphology and fabric of new cities is generally defined by the master plans, prepared for the city, based on; site, climate, culture, functions and projected population. Capital city of Chandigarh holds distinction of having two different master plans prepared for the city. First plan prepared by Albert Mayer & Mathew Nowicki and second evolved by Le-Corbusier. Currently, city stands developed based on Corbusier's plan. Both plans remain different and distinct, in vision, intent and contents, using different approach to; planning of city, neighbourhood planning, traffic and transportation and planning of shopping, housing and green spaces. Looking at the vision, intent, contents, structure and basic fabric, paper tries to compare two master plans and tries to visualise and bring out what the city would have gained and lost, had the first master plan of Mayer and Nowicki been implemented to develop the capital city.

Keywords: *Master Plan, Mayer, Nowicki, Corbusier, superblock, sector*

INTRODUCTION

Chandigarh, as a city, has been, globally and locally, recognised for its distinct urban planning, innovative architecture, unique quality of life, state of art infrastructures and sustainable development besides being recognised as a city, which remains different, distinct and unique, locally and globally. Despite numerous distinctions, little is known about the genesis and origin of the unique city of Chandigarh. The entire credit for the uniqueness of city and its glory as a well-planned and designed city, has been bestowed upon Le-Corbusier, the author of second master plan. Little is known, understood and appreciated about the valuable contribution made by the first team, comprising of Albert Mayer and Mathew Nowicki, who worked on the city, prepared its first master plan, detailed the super-block, planned the capitol and city centre besides doing numerous studies for planning of basic infrastructures. In addition, first team is also credited with the spatial positioning of four major components of the city beautiful namely; Capitol, City Centre, University and industrial area; in the first Master Plan prepared for the city.

Looking at the entire context of the planning and designing of the capital city at Chandigarh, it needs to be understood and appreciated that Chandigarh remains the product and synthesis of just not one master plan but two master plans, prepared for the city. First Master Plan of Chandigarh owe its evolution to the team

comprising of American Architect Albert Mayer and Ar. Mathew Nowicki, a polish architect settled in Tokyo. The first plan evolved for the city was a leaf -shaped plan, having ring and radial pattern, drawing inspiration from the leaf of tree. It was stated that contours and ever-expanding profile of the site selected, clearly demand that city must go on expanding, as it moves from North to South. First master Plan, based on super-block as the basic unit of planning, was the plan which catered to the total development of the city, housing its entire population of half a million. **(Fig 1).**

It needs to be understood and appreciated that site for capital city was already selected before foreign experts were hired for planning of Capital City. Credit for selecting the site of the city goes to the wisdom, knowledge, understanding, expertise of Er. Parmeshwari Lal Verma, first Chief Engineer of Capital city. There was no involvement of any outside expert while selecting the site. Playing the role of sheet anchor, Er. Verma was not only described as the ‘Soul of Chandigarh’ by Le Corbusier but has also been credited with playing critical role in the planning and execution of the capital city. He is also credited with preparing the project report detailing the requirements for setting of new capital city, creation of Sukhna lake, relocation of Punjab University, evolving development controls and shaping city infrastructures besides making Chandigarh a distinct reality. City was planned on the analogy of garden city.

Fig. 1: First Master Plan of Chandigarh- Mayer & Nowicki.

Sudden death of Mathew Nowicki, in an unfortunate plane crash in the night of August 31/September 1, 1950, changed the destiny of Chandigarh. Looking at the quantum of work, Ar. Albert Mayer expressed his inability to carry out the planning and designing work of the capital city of Chandigarh, in the absence of Mathew Nowicki. This necessitated the selection of second team led by Le-Corbusier duly supported by, Pierrie Jenerette, Maxwell Fry and Jane B Drew, to take over the charge of planning and designing of the new city.

1.5 Despite the fact, Corbusier was commissioned to implement the first Master Plan, prepared by Albert Mayer &

Mathew Nowicki, still Corbusier changed the contour, profile and basic unit of planning, by evolving a new Master Plan. Second Master Plan of Chandigarh, prepared by- Le Corbusier- a Swiss Architect settled in Paris, stands implemented on site. (Fig 2). Present city owes its existence and glory to the second Master Plan, which was said to be prepared by Le-Corbusier in a short span of 96 hours, after having a feel of the site. Despite large variations in form, structure, profile and extent of city, second Master Plan prepared by Le- Corbusier display many things common with the first Master Plan, prepared by Albert Mayer and Mathew Nowicki.

Fig. 2: Second Master Plan of Chandigarh- Le- Corbusier.

Looking at the context of growth and development of Chandigarh, in the last 75 years of its existence, it becomes important that intent, contents and scope of two master plans should be compared for understanding the form, contours, planning, structure and fabric of the city, had the Mayer's master plan been implemented on the ground. This brief write up, tries to visualise and analyse how Chandigarh would have looked different and distinct, had Mathew Nowicki not died in the tragic air crash in the night of August 31/ September 1, 1950 and Le-Corbusier was not hired to implement the approved master plan of Albert Mayer. On the face, it can be observed that had Chandigarh been built based on the first master plan prepared by the Ar. Albert Mayer, the city would have looked different and distinct and operated differently, providing different quality of physical and social life. Paper tries to visualise, the impact, context of the first master plan of Chandigarh in terms of urban planning, designing, shape, size, planning of residential, areas, pattern of

traffic and transportation, landscaping etc on the capital city of Chandigarh.

JUXTAPOSING TWO MASTER PLANS

Comparing the master plans of Chandigarh Capital city by Albert Mayer and Le Corbusier will provide a great opportunity and help us to look at, critically and objectively, at the process, intent, content of the evolution of 20th-century urbanism. While both plans aimed and focused on creating an unencumbered new capital city, free from the traditions of the past and a role model for the future urban planning in India, it can be seen and appreciated that their fundamental philosophies and approach related to planning, form, flow, structure of basic unit of neighborhood, constituting a city and defining vision, basic philosophy, approach, social and physical fabric, differed significantly.

It will be appropriate to state that the text of the paper is based on the limited availability of the enormous work done, by

the first team in the planning, designing of Chandigarh, in the public domain. To do justice to the subject, it will be important that more research should be needed by the researchers, thinkers and professionals for bringing out and deciphering the valuable contribution made by the team led by Albert Mayer & Mathew Nowicki. In addition, Chandigarh administration, should also place all the work done by the Mayer's team in the public domain, so that appropriate justice is done to the recognition of valuable contribution made by them in the context of planning and development of the capital city.

Based on the data, studies, documents and research made, two plans can be compared in following terms;

Context & Form

- First plan, prepared by Albert Mayer and Nowicki, shows the impact and influence of principles and pattern of American planning with basic residential unit defined by Superblock (500mx1000m). Accordingly, first plan based on the analogy of leaf following the Radburn principle, used curved roads to define the city profile, considering the site and valuing/respecting the prevailing natural topography. Focus of the plan was to create a "garden city", having genesis in informal living and creating village-like social fabric. Primary unit of Master Plan was super-block which had physical dimensions of 500mx1000m and an area of 50 Hectare
- Second Master plan, prepared by Le Corbusier, shows distinct influence of French planning. Based on the rectilinear grid, Corbusier viewed the city as a biological entity, based on the human analogy with: "Head" (Capitol Complex), the "Heart" (City Center), and the "Lungs" (Leisure Valley). Second Master Plan is largely

influenced by vision and thought of CIAM- International Congress of Modern Architects- a forum created by group of eminent architects headed by Corbusier - which worked on defining the principles and approach to planning, designing and circulation of future cities of machine age/ industrial era. Fabric of the second Master Plan was woven around Sector, as container of life for 24 hours, having physical dimensions of 800mx1200m and an area of 96 Hectares.

- Most obvious and critical difference between two master plans can be seen in the geometric transformation envisioned for the city, migrating and graduating from a curvilinear, organic layout to a rigid, orthogonal grid. First plan would have made city more traditional and vernacular with large traditional Indian components involved in the planning and designing of the city. Second master plan, inspired by Roman rigid geometry of city planning, has made the city of Chandigarh, more formal in its planning, development, living and culture.
- Difference between planning of two master plans can also be stated in terms of, Mayer's "American Garden City"- led plan and Corbusier's "CIAM-inspired Modernism". Difference in two plans clearly represents a critical difference, prevailing in the 20th-century ideology and philosophy related to urban planning, led by various school of planning thoughts. While different planning theories, concepts and schools of thought believed in creating self-sufficient and low-density capital city, but the approach used followed different and distinct approach, options and paths for achieving the agenda.
- Looking critically and objectively at two master plans, it can also be concluded that, if Mayer's master plan

pointed to the creation of softer and more landscaped city, Corbusier's Master plan is credited with putting a bold, legible, and highly organized urban fabric. Even though Corbusier's grid iron plan has been criticized for being, too rigid and monotonous at city level, but his neighborhood planning, showcased in the form of a sector, remains one of the most valued and innovative mechanism of creating a well-organized and socially vibrant human living at local level in India.

- Comparing two plans in vision, grains, culture and structure, it can be observed that, If Mayer's plan appeared more "human-centric" in social fabric; Corbusier's plan has been valued to provide the administrative clarity and architectural identity, besides creating a sense of monumentality.
- Despite difference in approach, Corbusier inherited several core concepts from Mayer's plan. Both plans rejected the high-rise "Ville Radieuse" model in favor of a low-rise, horizontal city, necessitated by the budgetary and technological constraints existing in India/Punjab of 1950s

Land Optimisation

- For setting up new city, availability and utilisation of land invariably remains critical issue. While comparing two master plans in terms of area used for the city, it can be observed that Mayer's plan was more land inefficient and consumed more land when compared with the Corbusier's Plan. Mayer projected a total land requirement of 18,000 Acres for housing the planned population of 5,00,000 residents. Higher land component for the city can be attributed to; Mayer opting for free-flowing form for planning of city, using low population density and

envisioning Chandigarh, as a garden city.

- Corbusier's Master Plan for the city placed total requirement at 15,000 Acres as against 18,000 Acres, projected for housing the same population. Had the Mayer's master plan been implemented, the city would have consumed additional 3000 acres of land over and above what city has used today. Reduction in the Chandigarh, in the second master plan can be attributed to the fact that Corbu used rigid geometric grid iron pattern and differential density pattern to make city more compact as against free-flowing form used by the Mayer.
- In addition, due to fear of being uprooting, local farmers and landowners were vehemently opposing the setting up of new Capital city at the selected site and acquisition of land identified for the new city. To pacify the agitating farmers, government of Punjab agreed to reduce the total land required for the city. For achieving the objective government of Punjab & Corbusier not only agreed to reduce the physical size of the city but also decided to take up the development of city in two different and distinct stages to initially minimise the land component for capital city. Accordingly, the land requirement were scaled down to 9000 Acres for the first stage of development of the city as against 18.000 projected earlier for the city.
- Master Plan of Le-Corbusier also scores over the Mayer's Plan in terms of land utilisation. Corbusier not only reduced the quantum of total land required for setting up of city by 3000 Acres, by making it more compact and land efficient but also envisioned that even for housing additional population beyond 5,00,000, city will not require any additional land. Conceptualising Chandigarh as a finite city, Corbu plan

proposed accommodating additional population beyond 5,00,000 within the first stage of development, by increasing density and creating more housing stock.

Phasing

- Chandigarh capital city is known for its development to be taken up in distinct phases, duly marked and distinguished by; amount of land to be acquired, population to be housed, density to be achieved, infrastructures/ services to be provided, institutions to be housed etc. However, phasing of city of 0.5 million population was never part of development strategy of the Mayer's plan, whereas phasing became important, valuable and critical part of city development in the Corbusier's Master Plan.
- Considering the continued opposition and prolonged protests of farmers against acquiring their land along with village Abadi area, it was considered prudent that, for partially meeting demand of the agitating farmers, quantum of land to be acquired for the capital city of Chandigarh in the first go must be minimised. Further, because Chandigarh was being visualised as a government city, which has limited economic and growth triggers and potential, city development needs to be staggered and phased. Accordingly, rather than opting for the development of the entire city in one go, it was felt prudent to phase the city development in distinct stages. This gelled with the then prevailing financial situation of the state of Punjab, having limitation/paucity of resources, to fund the development of the new capital city, due to partition in the year 1947.
- In the phasing option, first stage of city development- S-1, was conceived to be low density development, providing for iconic/ state of art development, for

creating a distinct image and brand for Chandigarh, locally and globally, so that city is recognised and valued for its quality of planning, development, environment, human living and infrastructures. Accordingly, S1 was planned to house 1,50,000 people in an area of 9,000 Acres. It was also decided that once first stage(S1) of the city development gets going, by housing major proportion of planned population and city achieves global recognition and branding, only then second stage of development should be taken up. Accordingly, second stage, S-2, was planned to be high density development, housing 3,50,000 people in a limited area of 6,000 Acres, for achieving the ultimate population of 5,00,000 for the capital city. However, Corbusier's Master Plan went further and provided for Stage three - S-3 of development, involving re-densification of Stage-One (S-1), for housing additional population when city population will exceed the designed population of 5,00,000. Accordingly, city was layered in different pattern, with density increasing, as one move from North to South. (Fig 3.)

- As it stands today, Chandigarh displays large variations in the development of SI & S2, in terms of density, housing, infrastructures, traffic and transportation, congestion, quality of life and available services. Despite development of two stages of development involving S-1(Low density) and S-2(High Density) , and city exceeding designed population of 5,00,000, development of S-3, - Re-densification of S-1, still remains a dream confined on papers only. Le-Corbusier wrote to the Punjab Government in the year 1964, that time has arrived to work out policy and prepare technical solution for achieving the agenda of

dedensification of stage one, but neither the letter was replied nor any action was initiated to evolve options to re-densify stage one(S1) of the city. In fact, led by post 1966 re-organisation of the state of Punjab, Chandigarh capital project area has been enlarged, contrary to the concept of finite city), by adding the residual land, falling between Chandigarh UT and state of Punjab (Mohali Township). In addition, city has also added more area by creating an IT City on the east of the city.

- Looking at the entire context of development of Chandigarh capital city, Mayer's Master Plan provided for more rational, equal and equitable

distribution of population over the entire city, when compared with the Corbusier's master plan, which has created differential pattern of density, housing, infrastructures and services in two stages of development. Two Stages of development, have created distinct pattern of growth and development, duly marked by dualities and contradiction and positivity and negativities. Stage-2 of the city development remains marginalised, muted and diluted in terms of infrastructures, services, amenities, size of residential plots, quality of education/healthcare institutions and even value of the property when compared to S1 of the city.

Fig. 3: Phasing-Stages of Development in Second Master Plan of Chandigarh- Le-Corbusier.

Major Components of City

- Despite having difference in approach, intent, content, scope, shape, size, planning, transportation etc, Master Plans prepared by the two teams led by Albert Mayer and Le-Corbusier also share number of commonalities.
- Both Master Plans, agree in terms of the physical location of the four major elements of the Capital city—Capitol, City Centre, University and Industrial area in the Master Plans. However, In the Le- Corbusier Master Plan -- the position of capitol Complex was shifted to the north-west- for spacing the creation of the great artificial water body- Sukhna lake in the city.
- Despite sharing commonalities, striking difference between the two master plans is also visualized in the positioning and treatment of the Capitol Complex. Mayer's plan placed the government buildings in the east of the city, based on the premise of centrality, easy accessibility and close integration of Capitol complex into the urban fabric, to promote a sense of belonging and proximity. In addition, site was placed close to the Sukhna lake for integration of complex with the water body. Considering the reality of the vision and concept, Mayer's Plan would have made Capitol complex much softer, eco-friendly, cleaner and greener with Sukhna becoming integral part of its planning and designing process.
- Comparing capital with head and considering it highly sacred among institutions, Corbusier isolated the complex by separating it from the city. Enveloped in massive green, Corbu placed the complex by shifting and positioning it against the Shivalik Hills, for creating monumental space at the terminus of one of the important city roads, namely Jan Marg, emphasizing the importance of the institutions of democratic governances

in urban planning. Corbu was largely said to be influenced by Greek planning of cities in positioning Acropolis on the highest and most visible/critical place of the city.

- In determining location of the City Centre (Heart) Mayer in its master plan had envisioned it a smaller, more traditional "City Core" that served as a business district, whereas Corbusier, considered City Centre as the human heart, which pumps vital blood and makes city pulsate, perform and reform. Accordingly, Corbusier positioned "Civic Center" at the junction of two major city roads- Jana Marg & Madhya Marg. Corbu also designed the complex as a massive, pedestrianized plaza, reflecting the European "piazza, converted into Indian context.

Traffic and Transportation

- Considering the increasing level of urbanisation and rapid growth of automobiles, both the Master Plans provided focused solutions for rational flow of traffic within the new capital city. Both planners sought to solve the "machine age" problem of the automobile, but their solutions differed in nature, form and hierarchy.
- Keeping in view the prevailing topography of the site and need for keeping the speed of vehicles within safe limits, Mayer's Master Plan opted for curved and radial road pattern for catering to the issues related to traffic and transportation, both at city and local levels. Accordingly, Mayer used a localized, decentralized approach to city traffic, which was a combination of "loop" and cul-de-sacs, to create a framework, where automobiles and human beings could co-exist without any conflict.
- However, based on work done in CIAM, Corbusier's Master plan opted for a straight jacket grid-iron pattern

road network, based on a well-defined hierarchy of roads named, Rule of 7 Vs- Rui- da- vitante, later amended to include V8bc, to accommodate large population of two wheelers on the Indian roads. The system of Grid -iron roads adopted for the city was primarily based on distinct advantages of the system and the pattern followed by the Romans and Indus valley civilisation, in planning of their cities.

- Looking at the traffic and transportation mechanism, it can be visualised that Mayer's Master Plan, would have made urban mobility more informal, flexible and enjoyable, rather than too formal and rigid, as defined in the Corbusier's Plan.
- However, city would have missed the valuable well-defined hierarchy of roads, if the Mayer's plan would be made operational. City would have also missed numerous Paths and Margs, dictating the vocabulary of roads, named after the destination and cardinal directions, in which they were located, including; Janmarg, Madhya Marg, Uttar Marg, Dakshin Marg, Poorav Marg, Paschim Marg, Sarovar Path, Udyog Path, Vidya Path, Udhyan Path etc.
- Considering the fact that each Super block in the Mayer's plan was divided into three distinct parts, City would have much larger number of junctions/conflict points with large number of crossings, when compared to planning of Sector, which provided only one entry from each side, limiting the creations of number of junctions/conflict points on major roads.
- In Mayer's plan, city fabric was woven around two vertical axes running parallel besides four horizontal roads, which in case of Corbusier was replaced by one vertical and four horizontal Roads-Margs.

Neighbourhood Unit- Superblock Vs Sector

- Both the Master Plans, in the planning of the city, used the concept and philosophy of developing self-contained and self-sustaining neighborhood units for decentralization of various activities at local level. However, neighborhood units adopted in the master plans varied in shape, size, scale, planning and positioning of different amenities/services, in both the plans
- Mayer's Master Plan opted for Super-block, which was supposed to be self-contained unit centered around green spaces. The focus of Super-block planning was to promote cluster-type development, maintaining a more traditional social hierarchy in the housing layouts. The size of super block was kept 50 Hectares (500mx 1000m), divided into three distinct units. In terms of housing, Superblock provided for mixing of residential housing of various categories including- HIG, MIG and LIG, to make the neighbourhood unit a mix of all housing categories. **(Fig 4)**
- Corbusier master plan used Sector as the basic unit of neighborhood planning, which was planned and designed to be container of everyday life. Normal size of the sector was placed at 96 Hectares (800mx1200m). Each sector was planned and designed to be introverted, based on the analogy of a city within city, surrounded by high-speed traffic arteries, safe from traffic, having self-sufficiency in all basic material and social needs of day-to-day human living and yet connected with nature. **(Fig 5)**
- Considering the fact that size of the Sector in Corbusier plan was double when compared to that of Super-block, used in the Mayer's plan, adoption of Super-block in planning of city would have made Chandigarh physically

more integrated and socially more vibrant, due to small size of the neighbourhood unit and mix of the housing categories. In addition, smaller size would have reduced distance between home and basic amenities, making city more compact and would have promoted walkability on large scale, as compared to the Sector.

- In the planning of Super-block", Mayer and Nowicki followed the Radburn principle, based on which internal roads were made to curve to discourage through traffic. In the planning of Sector, Corbusier ignored the prevailing topography in favor of grid-iron pattern, with roads reaching every house in the Sector, which has led to large number of vehicles littering and has made sectors unsafe for pedestrians.
- Instead of four vertical and horizontal divisions of the Corbu sector (area 25 Hect appx), Mayer's super-block had only three horizontal divisions of 17 Hect. Reduced size of super-block would have made city physically more compact/walkable and socially more vibrant.
- Corbusier Master plan envisaged, horizontal connectivity of sectors through V4 shopping streets and vertical connectivity through green belts, running north-south, with adjoining sectors. Super blocks did not provide for any such linkages interconnecting them. Accordingly, City would have missed its major vertical greens, connecting them with nature and Shivalik range of hills, had Mayer's plan been implemented.

Fig. 4: Plan of a Neighborhood unit- Superblock – Albert Mayer--Design for a three- block district in which Housing was confined to the periphery with parkland placed in the centre and Schools sited in the park with Bazaar placed at the edge of the Super-Block.

Fig. 5: Plan of a Neighborhood unit- Sector – Corbusier-Planned introvert, safe from traffic, as a city within city, having one entry from each side, divided horizontally by shopping street, with flow green running north to south for connectivity with Shivalik Hills, schools located in green belt and self-contained and self-sufficient in all day to day needs.

Sukhna Lake

Chandigarh Lake has been the most valuable gift of the Corbu plan to the city beautiful. City Beautiful would have missed the most iconic, revered and valued water feature/ tourist hub --Sukhna Lake;

if Mayer's Master Plan would have been implemented. Mayer's Plan had envisioned making Sukhna Choe integral part of the Capitol complex by positioning the complex, using part of Sukhna bed. (Fig.6)

Fig. 6: Placement of Capital Complex in the Sukhna Bed- Mayer & Nowick.

- Called as the gift of creators to the people of Chandigarh, Sukhna Lake remains the most valuable contribution and salient feature of the Le-Corbusier's Master Plan. Relocating Capitol Complex to the extreme North, innovatively using low-lying Sukhna bed and constructing a barrage across the Choe, helped in create large water reservoir/ artificial lake for the city. In the absence of Sukhna Choe, city would have missed not only great water feature but would have missed large number of advantages provided by the Sukhna lake. Sukhna lake has helped in

not only promoting rainwater harvesting at city level but also has helped in ground water recharging, lowering down the temperature, in addition it has helped in promoting large-scale afforestation on the northern edge of the lake, due to large scale conservation and preservation undertaken in the catchment area of lake and its environs.

Shopping Street

- Looking at the contours of the Superbock having three parts, Mayer conceptualise Shopping area, with

shops placed on both sides of the road, much like old Indian cities. (Fig 7)

- Corbusier plan of the Sector made shopping street, as one of the most valuable parts of the sector planning. Besides providing entry to the sector and working as a connector between the adjoining sector, Shopping Street (named V4), housed both shopping and major institutions required at the local level. Shops were planned only on one

side of the street ie south-western side, so as to avoid criss-crossing of roads and making people safe while shopping on the V4 street.

- Going by the narrative, capital city of Chandigarh misses the walkability, safety, ambience, vibrancy and experience of shopping in a traditional Indian bazaar, provided in the Mayer's plan.

Fig. 7: Shopping- Tradition Indian Bazaar – By Albert Mayer & Nowicki.

Industries

Looking at Mayer's Plan, Industrial area would have been much smaller due to its positioning, with Sukhna Choe defining its outer edge when compared with the Corbusier plan, where Industrial area has been expanded beyond S1(stage one) in the southeast side along the extension of the city based on S2 development

Green Belt

Planned and designed on the analogy of a garden city, Mayer's Plan provided large green area in the new city. With two major green belts traversing vertically across entire city, Central core provided in the Mayer's plan, would have looked much greener when compared with Corbu plan.

For promoting adequate greenery, Corbusier plan opted for providing a major vertical green, along the central choe within the city, called Valley of leisure. Known for its valuable contribution, Leisure valley has helped in creating a series of gardens, providing space for morning walker, creating numerous playgrounds, stadiums for promoting sports and creating a dedicated space for housing museums etc. In addition, Leisure valley has also been used as a channel for stormwater drainage of the adjoining sectors. Corbusier Plan also ensured that , in addition to leisure valley, created at city level, each sector should have the benefit of accessing green within a walkable distance. Accordingly, provision of a dedicated green belt, running from North to South, has been made integral part of sector planning. Green belt provided in the sector helps in connecting the people/communities of different sectors to the nature ie. Shivalik range of hills.

Architecture

- Looking at the design of the buildings prepared by first team, it can be easily concluded that typology and architectural vocabulary of buildings would have been totally different and distinct, when compared with design of buildings prepared by the second team.
- If Corbusier and his team believed in creating a new vocabulary of Chandigarh architecture, necessitated by climate, cost, technology and local materials, Mayer and Nowicki believed in creating architecture which was embedded more in local ethos and culture. If Corbusier believed in monumental architecture for the capital complex using concrete as the material, such an approach was not visible in the buildings design prepared by the first team.
- Chandigarh, under second team, adopted different approach for designing public buildings and buildings for the common use including housing and public buildings. Second team valued the materials and the need for keeping the distinct identity of the materials used in the construction of buildings. That is the reason Chandigarh had large number of boxlike structures, exposed concrete and brick façade visible in majority of the buildings constructed in the first phase by the second team. However, no such quality is revealed in the design of buildings prepared by the first team led by Mayer.
- However, first team believed in creating distinct identity of buildings by adding landmarks, which element has been found to be missing in the design of second team. Building design done by first team appears to be more porous, whereas that of second team are found to be more compact. **(Fig 8, 9,10)**

Fig. 8: Proposed Design of the Chandigarh Railway Station- Mayer & Nowicki.

Fig. 9: Design of Residential Housing with Courtyard- Mayer & Nowicki.

Fig. 10: Proposed Design for Assembly Building; Mayer & Nowicki.

CONCLUSION/ WAY FORWARD

- Looking at the above narrative, it can be observed that master plan, prepared by the Mayer for the capital city of Chandigarh, had certain innovative ideas and features, which would have made the Capital city different and distinct. Detailed study and analysis of the first Master Plan, can provide valuable insight and learning in the art and science of urban planning, designing of the capital city. It will be valuable to look at the distinct features of Mayer's plan and analyse its impact on the planning, designing of Chandigarh city.
- After 75 years of launching the new city, it is time for the architects, planners, researchers, scholars, academicians, students and faculty, engaged in teaching-learning of the urban planning and architecture, to look analytically at the valuable work done by Mayer and Nowicki in preparing the First Master Plan for Chandigarh. Study and documentation would help in recognising their valuable contribution, in making of the great city of Chandigarh. In addition,

detailed study, proper documentation and carrying out objective and focused analysis of the work done by Mayer and Nowicki, would remain valuable for understanding their vision of shaping of the Chandigarh capital city.

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